

Automatic Rain-Sensing Wiper System for 4-Wheeler Vehicles

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ABSTRACT

Over the past two decades, the automotive industry has aggressively researched ways to exploit modern computing and electronic advances in the development of safety, reliability, and entertainment technologies for vehicles. With drivers exposed to an ever increasing number of distractions, automatic rain-sensing wiper systems become an even more appealing feature, as they work to minimize the time the driver must take his/her hands off the wheel. Most traditional systems offer intermittent as well as variable speed operation. The traditional wiper system however requires driver constant attention in adjusting the wiper speed. Traditional windshield wiper speed constantly varies according to time and vehicle's speed. Because the manual adjustment of the wiper distracts driver's attention, which may be a direct cause accidents. This is review paper for automatic wiper in various method and also explain the basic skeleton for adjust speed of wiper automatically cording to the amount of water on the windshield and in addition with also in advance removal of moisture inside the car while raining. The system activates the wiper to operate in full automatic mode and detect moister using CAN technology.

Keyword: Rain-Sensing Wiper System, automotive industry,

INTRODUCTION

A windscreen wiper or windshield wiper is a device used to remove rain and debris from a windscreen. Almost all motor vehicle, including trains, aircraft and watercraft, are equipped with such wipers, which are usually an essential requirement. A wiper generally consists of an arm, pivoting at one end and with a long rubber blade attached to the other. The blade is swung back and forth over the glass, pushing water from its surface. The speed is normally adjustable, with several continuous speeds and often one or more "intermittent" settings. Most automobiles use two synchronized radial type arms. It takes a lot of force to accelerate the wiper blades back and forth across the windshield so quickly. In order to generate this type of force, a worm gear is used on the output of a small electric motor.

The worm gear reduction can multiply the torque of the motor by about 50 times, while slowing the output speed of the electric motor by 50 times as well. The output of the gear reduction operates a linkage that moves the wipers back and forth. Inside the motor/gear assembly is an electronic circuit that senses when the wipers are in their down they are parked at the bottom of the windshield, and then cuts the power to the motor. This circuit also parks the wipers between wipes when they are on their intermittent setting. With drivers exposed to an ever increasing number of distractions, automatic rain-sensing wiper.

systems become an even more appealing feature, as they work to minimize the time the driver must take his/her hands off the wheel. These systems detect droplets of rain on the windshield and automatically turn on and adjust the wiper system in accordance to the level of precipitation. Current rain-sensing

systems use an optical sensor to detect the presence of water on the windshield, and relay wiper control data to the vehicle's body control module (BCM). Unfortunately, these optical rain sensors suffer from a small sensing area, are prone to false-positives, and are too expensive to be included as standard equipment in most vehicles.

Over the past two decades, the automotive industry has aggressively researched ways to exploit modern computing and electronic advances in the development of safety, reliability, and entertainment technologies. Despite this, automatic rain-sensing wiper systems are relatively uncommon in modern vehicles for a number of reasons. They are often too expensive, too unsightly, or too unreliable to be desired in new automobiles. Many attempts have been made at constructing an effective, reliable, and cheap rain detection and wiper control system for vehicles speed and intermittent interval automatically according to the amount of rain. To measure the amount of water usually use optical sensor. In this type of sensors uses the fact that the refraction angle and the amount of reflection of the light are different when the 2 windshield is wet. Even though optical sensors are used widely they have some disadvantage. One of disadvantages is the sensitivity to external light. Another problem is occurs when car drive at night or gone through tunnel and even in underground parking. For this many systems still activate the wiper when the car comes out of tunnels or underground parking lot. Another shortfall, maybe a major one is that the sensing area is a relatively small portion of windshield. Hence the system operates only with limited area. The wiper system may fail to activate when there are some raindrops on the driver's line of sight, but not on the sensing area. They are often too expensive,

too unsightly, or too unreliable to be desired in new automobiles.

For solving these problems, In this paper, we present the concept using a vision-based smart wiper system that a driver to collect visual information during precipitation this is done Using PIC microcontroller with CAN (Controller Area Network) facilities. Use of CAN controller because that combine the connection between windscreen wiper switch, windscreen wiper motor and windscreen wiper restoration machine, and related unit. This was originally developed for use in cars but now used in industrial automation and control applications. CAN is a high-integrity serial data communications bus for real-time control applications. CAN controller have master and slave system.

Slave system collect the information about like amount of rain, temperature, moisture from sensor and from various other unit. This information sends it towards mater for father processing. Master analysis that data and take a decision and make logic. The decision include at what speeded the wiper motor rotate, and check whether there is any change in outer and inner temperature if there is small changes then no action to be taken, and if there is vast changes in temperature then which will automatically make the respons to the presence of moisture,

Fig 1: System Implementation on Car

And according adjusts that temperature and remove moister inside car windshield.

The problem definition is to design a prototype for a PIC microcontroller (PIC18F2580) based vision system aid in windshield assembly which controls the windshield wiper speed based on the amount of water. For this a comprehensive study of sensors, actuators and mechanical design was done. Development of hardware module and the software has progress. The basic method used for designing the circuit is that a rain level sensor will detect the amount of rain and give the signal to the controller.

Automatic Wiper system:

Vehicles are now available with driver-programmable intelligent (automatic) windscreen wipers that detect the presence and amount of rain using a rain sensor. The sensor automatically adjusts the speed of the blades according to the amount of rain detected. Rain-sensing windscreen wipers appeared on various models in the late 20th century, one of

the first being Nissan's 200SX/Silvia. As of early 2006, rain-sensing wipers are optional or standard on all Cadillac and most Volkswagen, and are available on many other main-stream manufacturers.

2.1 Why Automatic Wiper

In the present automobiles the number of facilities is much higher. The driver has to concentrate on road while driving, and with increased traffic, things get frustrating. The features in the car like GPRS to trace the route, music system, air condition system etc may drive away the attention of the driver. Thus an effort has been made to reduce the effort put by driver in controlling the speed of the wiper and put more concentration on his driving. Since this system is put into use in many higher end cars and has been successfully working, an effort was made to reduce the cost of the system so that this system can be implemented in common economic cars where a common man can also enjoy the benefits. In section II, the detail explanation about designing aspects of the system is given. In section III the working procedure of the system is given. The section IV covers the calculations involved, algorithm and the supporting graphs. The Conclusion is drawn in Section V.

DESIGN

It was found that the rain sensor is the expensive unit in the present system and an effort is done in making a sensor which is reasonable by price, the Cup Sensor. The sensing device used here is basically a conical shaped cup with a tray on the top of the cup to collect maximum possible amount of water. The different views of the device are shown below.

When the rain begins and the visibility to the driver is reducing, the system has to trigger the wiper to wipe the water on the screen. It can so happen that the driver feels the need of wiper but because the floater has not reached the level of the probe the system may not begin its function.

FIG 2. The water collected at the bottom in a cup type rain sensor

Thus certain conditions were considered and the calculations were carried out for the placement of the probes at appropriate heights. Also there is a small opening at the bottom of the cup which eventually drains water from the cup. If the rate of filling is greater than rate of discharge of rain water than the water level rises to the next probe level and hence the wiper speed increases.

3.1 Construction

Many attempts have been made at constructing an effective, reliable, and cheap rain detection and wiper control system for vehicles. A perfect system could subtract one more task from the driver's workload, and allow them to better keep their eyes on the road and hands on the wheel during foul weather. Despite this, automatic rain-sensing wiper systems are relatively uncommon in modern vehicles for a number of reasons. They are often too expensive, too unsightly, or too unreliable to be desired in new automobiles. While a number of different design approaches have been made to improve upon these issues, none have been successful enough for the technology to become widely adapted in new vehicles. By far the most common rain detection method, and the one currently employed by Hyundai vehicles, is the use of an optical sensor.

These optical sensors function by transmitting an infrared beam at an angle through the windshield and measuring the reflection to determine the presence of water. This is a relatively difficult task, requiring complex circuitry and precision manufacturing. Optical sensors are thus somewhat expensive and can produce false readings when dirt or other particles on the windshield cause a reflection mimicking that of rain. Because it relies on an infrared beam for detection, the optical sensor also suffers from a very small sensing area on the windshield, limiting its effectiveness in rapidly responding to light rain. In addition, the sensor housing is physically bulky, reducing its appeal in luxury vehicles. These issues can largely be mitigated by using a capacitive sensor rather than an optical one. Instead of sending an infrared beam through the windshield glass, a capacitive sensor works by emitting an electric field which can pass through the glass to interact with objects resting on it. Because water and other objects such as dirt or rocks interfere with the electric field in very different ways, the sensor will be less likely to be fooled if designed correctly. Unlike a standard capacitor, which confines the electric field lines between two conductors in a tight package, a capacitive sensor allows the field lines to spread out, and is designed to maximize the fringing of the electric field lines away from the conductors.

Fig 3. Fringle field lines extending from sensor traces with wind shield These electric field lines are known as “fringe fields”, and are vital to the operation of a capacitive sensor. Because they extend away from the conductors, which are typically just copper traces laid out flat on a printed circuit board (PCB), the fringe fields can be interacted with by other

objects. When conductive or dielectric objects interfere with these fields, it changes the capacitance of the capacitive sensor, as seen in Figures 1 and 2. This change in capacitance can then be detected via circuitry and used to modulate an output signal. Capacitive sensors can detect the presence, position, and type of conductive or dielectric material interfering with their fringe fields. When multiple capacitive sensors are connected in an array, they can also be used to detect movement of a conductive or dielectric object.

This effect is most commonly seen in capacitive touch pads, such as on popular products like the iPod Touch from Apple.

The electric field is created by applying an alternating current (AC) voltage to one of the conductors forming the sensor traces. A typical button sensor requires only two conductors, which never physically connect but are separated by a small distance and patterned into shapes. Depending on the application of the sensor, the sensor traces can take on a variety of different sizes and patterns. The layout of the traces is often designed to maximize the fringing fields over a given area. The traces, along with the materials surrounding them, also form the base capacitance of the system, typically along the order of 2 – 20 picot-Farads (pF) in magnitude. Base capacitance should be minimized when possible, as the change in capacitance resulting from fringe field interference is often less than 0.5 pF, and detection is easiest when the changing capacitance value is close to the base value. The idea to use capacitive-sensing to detect rain on a windshield is not entirely new, as seen in United States Patent US6094981, among others.

wipers according This allows the design to contain few parts, take up a small volume, and perform its job extremely well. It is significantly cheaper than the current optical sensor, with an estimated \$11.40 per unit cost, down from \$18 for the optical unit. It attaches to the interior of the windshield in the same location as the optical unit, but takes up less volume in the prototype unit and could be further refined if necessary in the production model for aesthetic purposes. Most importantly, the new sensor utilizes highly accurate 24-bit capacitance-to-digital converters and an on-board microcontroller to allow extreme accuracy and prevention of false-positives, improving the reliability of the device. These improvements in cost 10 and functionality will enable Hyundai to integrate the product into more vehicles in the future, further improving vehicle safety in the modern era.

4. FAST Diagram

4.1 Design a Capacitive-Sensing Circuit

Fig 4. A stable multi vibrator capacitive-sensing circuit (C1 = C sensor)

The first proposed design was to build a capacitive sensing circuit from basic components such as op-amps, comparators, and passive components. Due to experience in analog circuitry, the team realized that the capacitive sensor traces form a variable capacitor that changes as objects interfere with the 13 fringe fields. Many circuits exist that utilize the time-constant principle of an RC circuit to produce an output waveform. An a stable RC-multi vibrator circuit, as seen in Figure 3, produces a square wave output with a frequency varying with respect to the capacitance of the sensor traces when they are used as the capacitor.

This varying square wave could then be interpreted by a microcontroller, and compared to known responses from rain to determine appropriate wiper action.

WORKING OPERATION

The battery supplies the power to the sensor as well as rain operated motor. Wiper motor is automatically ON during the time of rainfall. The sensor is fixed in the vehicle glass. The conductive (Touch) sensor is used in this project. It senses the rainfall and giving control signal to the control unit. The control unit activates the wiper motor automatically. This operation is called “Automatic rain operated.

Fig 5. Block diagram of wiper arranging circuit system

The system can be summarized with the block diagram as shown in Figure. The components that require the most resources are the rain sensors,

Fig 6. Block Diagram of the System with Inputs and Outputs

Speech recognition hardware and software, powersupply, input/output signal modules and the windshield wiper mechanism.

All components will be linked by a PIC or MSP430 microcontroller. The rain sensors are separated into two categories for an accurate solution. The speech recognition module is powered by the HM2007 chip. The input signals the microcontroller and output module signals the windshield wiper mechanism. The control panel enables or disables the entire system without affecting any other circuit to which the system is attached.

SENSORS

6.1 Impedance Sensors

The impedance sensor to be implemented is the grid sensor shown in Figure. The sensor works by outputting a voltage, which is a function of how much water is in between the teeth. The closer the teeth, the more sensitive the sensor becomes. For the prototype, the separation distance will be adjusted between 0.10 mm and 1.0 mm to the desired sensitivity. At least two sensors will be made and placed at different locations on the glass to increase reliability.

Fig 7. Grid Sensor with varying electrical conduction due to water

A problem with this particular approach is that sometimes rain water is not very conductive; therefore, the output voltage will be very small and undetectable. One way around this problem is to use another impedance sensor that monitors capacitance instead of conductance. The sensor represented in Figure 4 is made of two thin copper plates placed around a glass, thus forming a capacitor. The presence of water changes the permittivity of the capacitor.

The sudden change results in a detectable current/voltage that is fed into a special MARE Windshield Wiper System ECE4007L02: Group 48 input signal module for amplification and standardization.

Obviously, the reliability and accuracy of the two impedance sensors discussed above can be improved by combining a multitude of them. However, they are vulnerable to corrosion, dirt, and other kinds of deposits.

6.2 Optical Sensors

The optical sensors will be used to bounce beams of light through the windshield, and look for disturbances in the beams caused by raindrops. Typically, a rain sensor will have an emitter that emits pulses of light, coupled into the windshield with a lens. These beams travel through the windshield at about 45 degrees. The beams are totally internally reflected by the outside surface of the windshield, so they bounce back into the sensor. The sensor then detects the reflected beams and measures them. If rain drops are present on the outside surface of the windshield, some of the beams escape and this reduces the intensity of the beams. The detector will measure this reduction in intensity and communicate that to the rest of the system that actuates the windshield wipers

APPLICATIONS

- ❖ It is used in four wheeler
- ❖ It is used in aircraft
- ❖ It is used in train
- ❖ It is used in six wheeler

ADVANTAGES

- ❖ Low cost automation project.
- ❖ Free from wear adjustment.
- ❖ Less power consumption.
- ❖ Operating principle is very easy Installation is simple.
- ❖ It is possible to operate manually/automatically by providing On/Off switch
- ❖ Sensor cost is very low due to the use of conductive sensor.

CONCLUSION

Our Automatic multispeed rain operated wiper system works well with conductive sensor. As future extraction work the same can be carried out by optical sensor. As far as accuracy of the system is concerned it is more accurate than conductive sensor. But the reason for not using optical sensor is because due to higher cost

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